

DeepLabCut tutorial

[Society of Integrative and Comparative Biology](#)
Phoenix, Arizona

**NOTE: some videos have been
removed from this pdf version!**

Mathis Group
computational neuroscience & AI

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Massive diversity of animals

Behavior is highly diverse

We need to reduce the problem to meaningful quantifications

Pixel Representation

Pose Estimation
Algorithm

Subject 1
Keypoints

Subject 2
Keypoints

Keypoint Representation

Marker-based pose estimation

Bernstein, 1920

Vargas-Irwin et al. 2010

MoDeep – *starting 2014*
 DeepPose
 Conv. PoseMachines

...
 DeeperCut
 OpenPose

...
*> 10,000 papers on human
 pose estimation with Deep
 Learning*

Appealing properties:

- Work “in the wild”
- Robust (backgrounds, individuals, etc)
- Relatively fast
- No body model
- No (manual) parameter tuning

deep neural networks

train

**A lot of labeled
 images (>10⁶ joints!)**

DeepLabCut: a toolbox for markerless pose estimation via transfer learning

A. Mathis M.W. Mathis* and Bethge*
Nature Neurosci, 2018

How little training data is required?

A. Mathis M.W. Mathis* and Bethge*
Nature Neurosci, 2018

Generalization to novel mice

Example of generalization: novel mouse tracking

A. Mathis M.W. Mathis* and Bethge*
Nature Neurosci, 2018

Let's dig into the nitty gritty

Machine learning system:

- Architecture
- Objective (task)
- Learning algorithm
- Data

Basic convolution (“same”)

Strided convolution

Strided **de**convolution

Keypoint Detector (Segmentation mask)

- Given: a ground truth coordinate (x_j, y_j) for the body joint j
- Construct a ground truth *scoremap* $s_j(x, y)$

$$s_j(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \|(x, y) - (x_j, y_j)\|_2 \leq R \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

EPFL Precise Keypoint Localization (Location Refinement)

- Inspired by bounding box regression in Overfeat [Sermanet et al, 2014] and Fast R-CNN [Girshick, 2015]

Regress the offsets

$$\Delta x = x_{part} - x$$

$$\Delta y = y_{part} - y$$

Multi-Task ConvNet

- Minimize the combined loss with SGD (with Momentum)
- Perform augmentation during training

How does markerless pose estimation work?

Key Features:

- Data augmentation
- Model architecture
- Optimization

Confidence readout (score-maps)

A. Mathis M.W. Mathis* and Bethge*
 Nature Neurosci, 2018

Transfer learning enables pose estimation with less data

Only a few examples (10-200)
for most applications

Andrew Ng

Locomotion
3D tracking of limbs

R. Warren (Sawtell lab)
Columbia University

Pellet reaching task

D. Leventhal Lab
University of Michigan

SICB-DLC

Whisker tracking

A Erskine (Hires lab)
USC

Pupil tracking

T. Vaissiere
Scripps

J Bonaiuto (Ferrari lab) CNRS

DeepLabCut:
a software package for
animal pose estimation

use our Jupyter Notebooks, Google Colab, or work in the terminal!

Data Augmentation: how to get the most out of your data!

tensorpack

imgaug

scale-crop

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Pose estimation for multiple animals

The idea: learn to predict "limbs"

EPFL Multi-Task Deep Convolutional Network

- Minimize the combined loss; segmentation + vector field
- Transfer learning (ConvNet pre-trained on object recognition)
- Perform augmentation during training

EPFL Multi-Task DCN (DLC 2.2)

Location Refinement
Smooth L_1 loss

Bodyplan agnostic graph optimization

Learn to predict:

- **Bodyparts**
- Limbs (= costs for associations)

Which limbs should be learned?

Automatic
skeleton selection

EPFL Novel data driven method outperforms baseline methods (giving SOTA perf)

mAP performance

Multi-Task DCN (DLC 2.2)

Individual identification performance

Identification of individuals

3D pose estimation?

AcinoSet: A 3D Pose Estimation Dataset and Baseline Models for Cheetahs in the Wild

Pose Type	Metric	TRI	EKF	FTE
Run	RMSE	28.24	3.40	2.76
	SEM	0.26	0.03	0.03
	NRMSE	0.17	0.02	0.02
Dive	RMSE	76.35	39.40	38.44
	SEM	0.70	0.36	0.35
	NRMSE	0.56	0.29	0.28

EKF: extended Kalman filter
 FTE: full trajectory estimation

Can DeepLabCut be applied in real-time?

Providing real-time feedback in experiments

- <https://github.com/DeepLabCut/DeepLabCut-live>

#Initialize model:

```
from dlclive import DLCLive  
my_live_object = DLCLive("/exportedmodel/directory")
```

run inference:

```
my_live_object.init_inference(my_image)  
pose = my_live_object.get_pose(my_image)
```


Example experiment

modelzoo.deeplabcut.org

Example model in the DLC model zoo

(added 3 days after the pre-print!)

What to do with DLC output?

How to use DeepLabCut?

DeepLabCut workflow

Train DNN

Create a project,
extract frames, +
GUIs to label your data

Select + Train your
deep neural network

Evaluate network
performance

(active learning + GUIs
if improvement needed)

Run inference on
new videos,
create labeled videos,
+ plot your results!

refine?

Steps 7 and 8

GUI: labeling

- Unique label 1
- Unique label 2
- Unique label 3

Step 9: check labels!

Frames extracted from video
(any species can be used)

Steps 1-5

Create project

Step 6

Extract frames

Label frames (GUI)

Step 10

Create training datasets

Step 11

Train network

Step 12

Evaluate network

Good results

Yes

Analyze video

Stop

Steps 13-15

Analyze novel videos

Merge datasets

Refine labels (GUI)

Extract outlier frames

Analyze video

Steps 16-18

GUI: refinement

- Unique label 1
- Unique label 2
- Unique label 3

nature
protocols

PROTOCOL

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-019-0176-0>

Using DeepLabCut for 3D markerless pose estimation across species and behaviors

Key commands

Operation	Command
Open IPython and import DeepLabCut (Step 1)	<pre>ipython import deeplabcut</pre>
Create a new project (Step 2)	<pre>deeplabcut.create_new_project('project_name', 'experimenter', ['path of video 1', 'path of video2', ...])</pre>

DeepLabCut 2.0 workflow

2D Project Folders

This is the master folder created when
you create a project (Step 1)

New (2D) videos for analysis

you can place new videos here, and then run:
`deeplabcut.analyze_videos(config_path,
folderpath, videotype='.mp4')`

Your 2D or 3D project “entry point” is through the `config.yaml` file
When you want to work on your project:

```
activate DLCenvName  
ipython  
import deeplabcut  
config_path = '/home/yourprojectfolder/config.yaml'
```

Frame extraction: deeplabcut.extract_frames(..)

Select videos to grab frames:

Use videos with image from:

- different sessions reflecting (if the case) varying light conditions, backgrounds, setups, and camera angles (etc).
- different individuals, especially if they look different (i.e. brown + black mice)

3 methods for frame extraction to create a labeled train/test set

Image based clustering (k-means)

Random temporal sampling (uniform)

GUI for manual frame grabbing

Label frames: deeplabcut.label_frames(..)

Label frames using the interactive GUI:

User instructions

1. Select one of the body parts from the radio buttons to add a label (if necessary change config.yaml first to edit the label names).
2. Right clicking on the image will add the selected label and the next available label will be selected from the radio button. The label will be marked as circle filled with a unique color.
3. To change the marker size, mark the checkbox and move the slider.
4. Hover your mouse over this newly added label to see its name.
5. Use left click and drag to move the label position.
6. Once you are happy with the position, right click to add the next available label. You can always reposition the old labels, if required. You can delete a label with the middle button mouse click.
7. Click Next/Previous to move to the next/previous image. User can also add a missing label by going to a previous/next image and using the left click to add the selected label. NOTE: the user cannot add a label if the label is already present.
8. When finished labeling all the images, click 'Save' to save all the labels as a .h5 file.
9. Click OK to continue using the labeling GUI.

OK

What bodyparts can be detected?

DLC has very large receptive fields (due to deep ResNet), so many visual features + geometric layout can be co

- Salient points (e.g. snout/tail base)
- Texture of objects
- Can teach the network to guess
- Geometric relationship
 - (e.g. left/right ear; whiskers!)

Playing magic tricks to deep neural networks
untangles human deception
by Zaghi-Lara et al. arxiv 2019

- Label (feature locations) **consistently**
- Errors are bad! (especially when only a few images are labeled)
- Left vs. right body parts can be dist. if full animal visible (due to large rec. fields), but flipped labels are problematic
- You can check labels by plotting (do this before training!)
- You can correct wrong labels manually with the labeling GUI

What network & augmentation method?

Network architecture:

- Network backbones: MobileNets V2, *ResNets*, *DLC-Rnet* & EfficientNets
- Scale (level of deconvolution) -> decrease stride for closely interacting animals and and when you want high resolution
- Differences: Inference & training speed, resolution

Pre-training (Weights):

- *ImageNet pretrained (the generalist)* -> see Mathis et al. 2021 WACV
- MPII-pose pretrained
- DeepLabCut model zoo

Training method:

- Learning rate & optimizer (Adam/SGD, batch_size, ...)
- Augmentation transformations (rotation, scaling, ...)

Online demo ... let's start training

DEMO:

https://github.com/DeepLabCut/DeepLabCut/blob/master/examples/COLAB/COLAB_DEMO_mouse_open_field.ipynb

Augmentation

Data Augmentation: how to get the most out of your data!

tensorpack

imgaug

scale-crop

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Evaluation: *Compare test RMSE and ideally your labeling error!*

Evaluation => look at test images!

a Example of the terminal output

```
deeplabcut.evaluate_network('<path of the proj. config file>', shuffle = [1], plotting=True)
```

```
Assessing accuracy of shuffle # 1 with 99 % training fraction.
Found the following training snapshots: [(200000, 0)]
You can choose among those for analysis of train/test performance.
Results for 200000 training iterations: 99 % train error: 4.81 pixels. Test error: 7.02 pixels.
with cutoff of 0.1: train error: 3.3 pixels. Test error: 5.2 pixels
```

b Examples of training images with Human and DeepLabCut labels

c Examples of test images with Human and DeepLabCut labels

d Examples of test images with Human and DeepLabCut labels

NATURE PROTOCOLS

PROTOCOL

Table 1 | Summary of commands

Evaluate the trained network (Step 11)	<code>deeplabcut.evaluate_network(config_path)</code>
Video analysis and plotting results (Step 11)	<code>deeplabcut.analyze_videos(config_path, ['path of video 1 or folder', 'path of video2', ...])</code>
Video analysis and plotting results (Step 12)	<code>deeplabcut.plot_trajectories(config_path, ['path of video 1', 'path of video2', ...])</code>
Video analysis and plotting results (Step 13)	<code>deeplabcut.create_labeled_video(config_path, ['path of video 1', 'path of video2', ...])</code>
Refinement: extract outlier frames (Step 14)	<code>deeplabcut.extract_outlier_frames(config_path, ['path of video 1', 'path of video 2'])</code>
Refine labels (Step 15)	<code>deeplabcut.refine_labels(config_path)</code>
Combine datasets (Step 16)	<code>deeplabcut.merge_datasets(config_path)</code>

Video analysis

New videos need **not** be added to the config.yaml!

Set *batch_size* in the config.yaml!

Trajectory visualization

```
deeplobcut.plot_trajectories(config_path, ['fullpath/analysis/project/videos/reachingvideo1.avi'])
```


Body parts plotted in space
(over all the frames)

All body parts across time (frames).
solid lines are Y and dashed lines are X

Every body part likelihood over time
(over all the frames)

Consecutive coordinate differences
(low values = minimal jumps across frames)

Trajectory filtering

```
deeplabcut.filterpredictions(config_path,['/videopath/mouse.avi'], p_bound=0.1, ARdegree=5, MAdegree=1)
```

Unfiltered:

Filtered (ARIMA model):

DeepLabCut 2.0 workflow

Active learning

- If there are errors in analyzed videos, you can correct those manually and re-train!
- Note you do not need to correct all errors (presumably some are fixed due to generalization)

```
deeplabcut.extract_outlier_frames(config_path, ['videofile_path'])
```

• Key arguments

```
outlieralgorithm: 'fitting', 'jump', or 'uncertain'
```

Select frames deviating from
a statistical model fit to the data

Select frames with jumps between consecutive frames $> \epsilon$ pixels

Select frames with confidences $< p_{bound}$

Random sampling

```
extractionalgorithm='uniform'
```

Clustering

```
extractionalgorithm='k-means'
```

a

Identification of outlier frames

Good frame

Putative outlier frame

b

Refinement of DeepLabCut-applied label location(s)

ZOOM

PAN

c

Label removal, i.e., from an occluded point

Multi-animal DLC

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DEMO:

https://github.com/DeepLabCut/DeepLabCut/blob/master/examples/COLAB/COLAB_3miceDemo.ipynb

DeepLabCut 2.2+ workflow

Tracking

Stitching

Corresponding commands:

```
dlc.analyze_videos( .. )
```

```
dlc.convert_detections2tracklets(...)
```

```
dlc.stitch_tracklets(...)
```

Refine tracklets GUI: deeplabcut.refine_tracklets()

How to use DeepLabCut?

<https://github.com/DeepLabCut/DeepLabCut-Workshop-Materials>

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+ >65 people on GitHub (Thanks!)

Questions?

Please get in touch!

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Open Source Code: <https://github.com/DeepLabCut/>
Tutorials, Data, Papers etc.: <https://deeplabcut.org>
User forum: <https://forum.image.sc/tag/deeplabcut>

NATURE PROTOCOLS

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Box 2 | Parameters of interest in the network configuration file, *pose_cfg.yaml*

Please note, there are more parameters that typically never need to be adjusted; they can be found in the default *pose_cfg.yaml* file at https://github.com/AlexEMG/DeepLabCut/blob/master/deeplabcut/pose_cfg.yaml.

- `display_iters`: An integer value representing the period with which the loss is displayed (and stored in *log.csv*).
- `save_iters`: An integer value representing the period with which the checkpoints (weights of the network) are saved. Each snapshot has >90 MB, so not too many should be stored.
- `init_weights`: The weights used for training. Default: `<DeepLabCut_path>/Pose_Estimation_Tensorflow/pretrained/resnet_v1_50.ckpt`. For ResNet-50 or 101, -- this will be automatically created. The weights can also be changed to restart from a particular snapshot if training is interrupted, e.g., `<full path>-snapshot-5000` (with no file-type ending added). This would re-start training from the loaded weights (i.e., after 5,000 training iterations, the counter starts from 0).
- `multi_step`: These are the learning rates and number of training iterations to perform at the specified rate. If the users want to stop before 1 million, they can delete a row and/or change the last value to be the desired stop point.
- `max_input_size`: All images larger with size width \times height $>$ `max_input_size*max_input_size` are not used in training. The default is 1500 to prevent crashing with an out-of-memory exception for very large images. This will depend on your GPU memory capacity. However, we suggest reducing the pixel size as much as possible; see Mathis and Warren²⁷.

The following parameters allow one to change the resolution:

- `global_scale`: All images in the dataset will be rescaled by the following scaling factor to be processed by the convolutional neural network. You can select the optimal scale by cross-validation (see discussion in Mathis et al.¹²). Default is 0.8.
- `pos_dist_thresh`: All locations within this distance threshold (measured in pixels) are considered positive training samples for detection (see discussion in Mathis et al.¹²). Default is 17.

The following parameters modulate the data augmentation. During training, each image will be randomly rescaled within the range `[scale_jitter_lo, scale_jitter_up]` to augment training:

- `scale_jitter_lo`: 0.5 (default).
- `scale_jitter_up`: 1.5 (default).
- `mirror`: If the training dataset is symmetric around the vertical axis, this Boolean variable allows random augmentation. Default is `False`.
- `cropping`: Allows automatic cropping of images during training. Default is `True`.
- `cropratio`: Fraction of training samples that are cropped. Default is 40%.
- `minsize, leftwidth, rightwidth, bottomheight, topheight`: These define dimensions and limits for auto-cropping.